

Amino acid and fatty acid composition of seed kernels of *Acacia leucophloea*

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Acacia leucophloea Willd. (Fam. : Leguminosae) seed kernels are found rich in crude protein (40.3%) and petroleum ether extracted oil (7.8%). There are seventeen amino acids in it, among which glutamic acid (566 mg/gN), aspartic acid (403 mg/gN) and arginine (402 mg/gN) are high in concentration. The fat comprises of high percentage of oleic acid (64.4%) and linoleic acid (20.1%).

Acacia leucophloea (Roxb.) Willd. grows abundantly in arid and semi-arid forests of India¹. Its stem bark is known for medicinal properties² and its heartwood contains *n*-octacosanol and β -amyirin³. The presence of prussic acid above critical levels in leaves, buds, flower and pods causes toxicity to the grazing animals⁴. Its seeds are free from prussic acid⁴ and are used with flour by the human beings in the event of scarcity in Rajasthan⁵. Owing to the plentiful availability of its seed in ranges with no input and scanty research work on this species of *Acacia*, the titled study was carried out.

Results and Discussion

The proximate analysis of the seed kernels exhibited 40.3% crude protein (CP), 14.2% crude fibre, 7.8% ether extract (EE), 6.5% ash and 31.2% nitrogen-free extract. The fat (ether extract) crude protein content in seed kernels could be compared to that of commonly available groundnut cake or linseed cake⁶. The amino acid pattern indicates the presence of essential and non-essential amino acids : glutamic acid (566), aspartic acid (403), arginine (402), leucine (299), glycine (266), lysine (206), proline (206), serine (190), valine (172), tyrosine (120), alanine (169), phenylalanine (160), isoleucine (140), threonine (177), histidine (114), cystine (86) and methionine (52 mg/gN).

The bright yellow oil (7.8%) was odorless. The fatty acid composition of the oil showed high percentage of oleic acid (64.4) followed by linoleic acid (20.2), palmitoleic acid (1.8), stearic acid (1.4), arachidic acid (1.3) and behenic acid (1.2%). Thus there was high degree of unsaturation (86.4%). The presence of linoleic acid being an essential fatty acid in significant amount is noteworthy for animal feed⁷. Furthermore, the presence of palmitic acid (9.7%) in fat enhances quality of feed for animal nutrition because of its efficient absorption in gut⁸.

Therefore, in view of the abundant availability in forests and nutritive ability of *A. leucophloea* seeds with low input these can be exploited as animal feed.

Experimental

The mature pods of *A. leucophloea* were collected during May from the Central Research Farm of the Institute. The seeds were separated from the pods and dried at room temperature for grinding. The seed kernel powder was analyzed for proximate principles⁹. The known weight of the defatted seeds powder was hydrolyzed with 6 N HCl and the hydrolysate was analyzed on amino acid analyzer (Durrum, D-500).

The powder seed was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) yielding a bright yellow oil, which was decolorized with Fuller's earth. The oil was saponified with 0.5 N alcoholic KOH. After removal of alcohol, the non-sap was separated by ether extraction. The fatty acids were liberated from the saponified part by hydrolysis with 10% H₂SO₄ in usual manner. The mixed fatty acids were converted to their methyl esters by treatment with diazomethane and resolved on the GLC using column, 10% DEGS on Chromosorb W, 3 m × 3 mm, column temperature 180°, injector temperature 225°, detector FID, carrier gas N₂ 60 ml/min. The fatty acids were identified by comparing the retention time with that of references.

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Note

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